

Ameliorative Effect of Diosgenin & Eugenol Against Streptozotocin-Induced Diabetic Neuropathy in Rats

Paswan Praveen Kumar^{1*}, Mr. Salaj Khare², Dr. Mihir Y. Parmar³, Zalak Dve⁴,
Devanshi Sharma⁵, Bhumika Parmar⁶, Palak Landge⁷

Corresponding Author^{1*}: Paswan Praveen kumar Department of Pharmacology, Krishna School of Pharmacy (Formerly, Babaria Institute of Pharmacy), Drs. Kiran and Pallavi Patel Global University, Krishna Edu Campus, Varnama, Vadodara, Gujarat, India.

ABSTRACT

This study presents the application of Traditional medicine has drawn a lot of interest when it comes to treating disorders like diabetic neuropathy (DN). The purpose of this work was to examine the possible therapeutic benefits of the flavanone diosgenin & eugenol in treating DN in rat models caused by streptozotocin. Following the successful induction of diabetes, four weeks after the induction of diabetes, either with or without therapy with diosgenin and eugenol, DN complications were assessed using a battery of behavioral measures. Serum biochemical tests including lipid profile, insulin, HbA1c%, and fasting blood glucose were measured. Furthermore, histology was performed on brain and pancreatic samples to examine structural changes. In the acetone drop test, the diabetic rats showed higher frequencies of paw withdrawal; however, in the plantar, hot plate, and tail flick tests, their rates were lower. Additionally, the diabetic rats displayed a changed proinflammatory level. Treatment with diosgenin and eugenol greatly enhanced these parameters and contributed to the restoration of the brain's and the pancreatic tissues' natural architecture. The results indicate that the neuroprotective qualities of diosgenin and eugenol may be related to their capacity to inhibit the excessive activation of inflammatory molecules and mediators. Specifically, both substances demonstrated neuroprotection against diabetic neuropathy and had a significant impact on behavioral performance in treated rats. Additionally, their combination produced synergistic benefits.

Keywords: Diosgenin, eugenol, streptozotocin, neuronal specific indicators, histology, diabetic neuropathy.

1. INTRODUCTION

According to estimates from the International Diabetes Federation, 425 million people globally have diabetes¹, making it the biggest pandemic of the twenty-first century worldwide². Diabetes affects 30 million Americans, 115 million Chinese, and 73 million Indians³. These figures pale in comparison to the projected 388 million people in China⁴, 133 million in India⁵, and 85 million in the United States⁶ who have prediabetes.

Diabetic neuropathy (DN) is the main consequence of long-term diabetes and one of the abnormalities it produces. A set of clinical symptoms resulting from injury to the peripheral and autonomic nerve systems are by far the most common consequences associated with diabetes. These disorders, which are sometimes referred to as distinct types of neuropathy, affect up to half of all diabetics and are brought on by localized and diffuse nervous system injury⁷. Type 1 diabetes is an insulin-dependent form of the disease where the immune system of the body targets the pancreatic β -cells, which secrete insulin, specifically. On the other hand, cells may either become resistant to insulin or cease to respond to it in type 2 diabetes (insulin-independent diabetes)⁸. Diabetic sensorimotor polyneuropathy (DPN) is more common in those with type 1 and type 2 diabetes⁹.

The most common form of diabetic neuropathy — distal symmetric polyneuropathy is the focus of this Primer, and as such will be referred to as diabetic neuropathy throughout. Distal symmetric polyneuropathy manifests with a ‘stocking and glove’ distribution, whereby the hands and lower limbs are commonly affected. Other diffuse neuropathies secondary to diabetes can occur (Fig. 1) and include the constellation of autonomic neuropathies, such as cardiac autonomic neuropathy, gastrointestinal dysmotility and diabetic cystopathy and impotence.

Figure 1.1: Patterns of diabetic neuropathy nerve damage. (part a); mononeuropathy (part c); autonomic neuropathy or treatment-induced neuropathy (part d); and radiculoplexopathy or radiculopathy (part b). The distribution of DSP and small-fibre-predominant neuropathy is similar, although there are differences in the neurological examination and the findings of tests on nerve conduction velocity.

1.1 Etiology and risk factors

The primary cause of diabetic neuropathy is elevated plasma glucose levels (diabetes mellitus), which typically impairs neuronal communication and weakens the blood vessels that nourish and oxygenate the nerves¹⁰. Other variables that contribute to a disturbed metabolic pathway that ultimately results in increased ROS production due to modified mitochondrial redox status¹¹ include insulin resistance, hyperglycemia, and dyslipidemia. These conditions ultimately cause axonal vitality to be lost. Therefore, neuronal dysfunction and eventual cell death can undoubtedly result from oxidative stress and inflammation¹². Additional risk factors encompass age, weight, BMI, HbA1c levels, diabetic retinopathy, 2-h GCP, length (duration) of diabetes, tobacco use, hypertension, fasting plasma glucose, BUN levels, and so on¹³⁻²¹. Early alterations in type "C" unmyelinated fibers in diabetic neuropathy cause pain, physical sensitivity, allodynia, and loss of feeling in the body's distal regions (the foot and toe) mostly as a result of axonal degradation^{22, 23}. Peripheral neuropathy, autonomic neuropathy, focal neuropathy, and proximal neuropathy are the four

Primary classifications of diabetic neuropathy according to the affected part²⁴.

About 50% of people with diabetes suffer from peripheral neuropathy, a condition that primarily affects and is painful to the motor and sensory nerves around the periphery of the brain²⁵. The whole autonomic nervous system is affected by autonomic neuropathy; focal neuropathy causes isolated mononeuropathies, radiculopathy, or polyradiculopathy, whereas proximal neuropathy causes severe unilateral anterior thigh pain, quadriceps muscle weakness, and loss of knee jerk^{26, 27}.

1.2 Mechanisms/pathophysiology

Diabetes-related peripheral neuropathy has a complicated etiology that is characterized by several vascular and metabolic variables. A distinct neurodegenerative condition of the peripheral nervous system, diabetic neuropathy primarily affects sensory, autonomic, and eventually, to a lesser degree, motor axons. There is disagreement over how diabetes mellitus affects sensory neurons. The peripheral terminal sensory axons shrink and "die back" in progressive diabetic neuropathy, whereas the perikarya (cell bodies) are largely preserved. It is controversial, nevertheless, whether damage initially affects the neuron perikarya that live in the dorsal root ganglia (DRG) and support the axons, or the peripheral axons and the Schwann cells that are connected to them. (Fig. 2).

Figure 1.2: The peripheral nerve system and diabetic neuropathy's changes.

Our body's regular physiological processes keep blood plasma glucose levels at their ideal range. However, diabetes and its associated problems are caused by any modification to these processes. The formation and progression of diabetic neuropathy are attributed to four major routes. These pathways, which are called the Polyol pathway, Intracellular synthesis of Advance Glycation End Products (AGE) precursors, Protein Kinase C (PKC) activation, and Hexosamine pathway, show the metabolic anomalies of neuron physiology. Elevated glucose levels trigger the activation of the polyol pathway, whereby the enzymes aldose reductase and sorbitol dehydrogenase catalyze the conversion of glucose to fructose and sorbitol to sorbitol, respectively. Aldose reductase uses up NADPH in the process of converting glucose to sorbitol, which reduces the amount of glutathione produced and increases the vulnerability of cells to intracellular oxidative stress. The polyol pathway's increased activity also lowers myo-inositol, which eventually causes diabetic neuropathy²⁸⁻³¹. AGE precursors react through three mechanisms: first, they alter intracellular proteins, which disrupts gene transcription; second, they diffuse into cells, causing cellular dysfunction; and third, they modify circulating proteins in the blood, activating AGE receptors, which produces growth factors and cytokines, ultimately leading to vascular pathology³². PKC needs to be phosphorylated in order to bind to its activating cofactor, diacylglycerol, whose synthesis is accelerated by high glucose concentrations. In order to disrupt axonal transport, activated PKC either up- or down-regulates the expression of certain genes, such as endothelin-1 or endothelial Nitric Oxide Synthase³³. Fructose-6 phosphate is redirected to other signaling pathways (Glycolysis: original pathway) through the hexosamine pathway. The enzyme glutamine: fructose-6 phosphate amido transferase (GFAT) converts fructose-6 phosphate to glucosamine-6 phosphate and then to UDP (uridine diphosphate) N-acetyl glucosamine, which, after binding to serine and threonine, causes a change in gene expression (Fig. 3)³⁴

Figure 1.3: Pathophysiological mechanism of diabetic neuropathy

1.2.1 Hyperglycaemia and hyperlipidaemia

Knowing how the peripheral nerve system uses substrates for energy is essential to comprehending the pathophysiology of diabetic neuropathy, particularly in the context of diabetes. Both glucose and fatty acids generate NADH and FADH₂ in Schwann cells, DRG neurons, and axons through glycolysis, the tricarboxylic acid cycle (for glucose), and β-oxidation (for fatty acids). Each cycle of β-oxidation produced by transporting long-chain fatty acids into Schwann cells results in one molecule of acetyl-CoA, which is then carried to the tricarboxylic acid cycle for the synthesis of NADH and FADH₂. But when there is an excess of substrate, as in diabetes, the transport mechanism gets saturated and acetyl-CoA molecules turn into acylcarnitines. The build-up of acylcarnitines exacerbates the continuous damage to the nervous system in diabetic neuropathy by being toxic to both Schwann cells and DRG neurons. When Schwann cells accumulate acylcarnitines, they discharge them

may cause axonal degeneration in Schwann cells, which has been linked to mitochondrial malfunction and an inappropriate integrated stress response.³⁵

Through Complexes I–IV, NADH and FADH₂ are moved throughout the mitochondria to facilitate oxidative phosphorylation, which produces ATP. Low concentrations of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which are quickly eliminated by intrinsic cellular antioxidants such as superoxide dismutase, glutathione, and catalase, are a consequence of oxidative phosphorylation.^{36–41} On the other hand, oxidative phosphorylation fails when there is an excess of substrate load, as in the case of diabetes. This results in a decrease in ATP generation and an increase in ROS levels, which in turn causes mitochondrial failure and damages Schwann cells and DRG neurons metabolically and oxidatively.^{42–43} Axonal disruption and damage are further encouraged by dysfunctional mitochondria, which provide insufficient energy and are unable to routinely traffic down axons.⁴⁴

Elevated glucose triggers glucose metabolism through the polyol and hexosamine pathways, leading to elevated reactive oxygen species and inflammation, respectively. This is mostly caused by damage to the mitochondria, which further exacerbates persistent nervous system malfunction⁴⁵. Many structural and functional proteins are glycosylated in response to elevated glucose levels, resulting in the production of advanced glycation end-products (AGEs). Pro-inflammatory chemicals and free radicals are released more readily when AGEs interact with the AGE-specific receptor (RAGE) to change gene expression and intracellular signaling. AGEs also cause altered or lost protein function.⁴⁶ Simultaneously, the excessive free fatty acids generated by β -oxidation in response to hyperlipidemia can harm the peripheral nervous system, especially Schwann cells, by generating reactive oxygen species (ROS) and causing both systemic and local inflammation through the activation of macrophages, which in turn produces cytokines and chemokines.⁴⁸ (Fig. 4).

Figure. 1.4: The pathophysiology of diabetic neuropathy.

1.3. Introduction to Plants

API

1.3.1. Binomial name : *Trigonella foenum-graecum*

Scientific classification:

Kingdom:	Plantae
Clade:	Tracheophytes
Clade:	Angiosperms
Clade:	Eudicots
Clade:	Rosids
Order:	Fabales
Family:	Fabaceae
Subfamily:	Faboideae
Genus:	Trigonella
Species:	<i>T. foenum-graecum</i>

Figure 1.5:(a) Fenugreek seeds contain active pharmaceutical ingredients such as (b) Diosgenin.

1. Fenugreek has long been used as a common herbal remedy in South and Central Asia, Africa, India, and these regions to treat a wide range of ailments, including diabetes and obesity. The white, light powder known as diosgenin saponin is the active component of fenugreek. Diosgenin saponin, which has antioxidative properties and plays a crucial role in treating the diabetic state through multiple mechanisms, such as β -cell renewal and insulin secretion stimulation, is believed to be the main bioactive component of fenugreek. Diosgenin also increases the amounts of peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor- γ (PPAR- γ) and CCAAT/enhancer-binding protein (C/EBP δ) mRNA transcription (10,12). Additional components of fenugreek include the amino acid 4-hydroxyisoleucine, which increases insulin secretion and lowers levels of total cholesterol, plasma triglycerides, and insulin.

1.4. Binomial name : *Syzygium aromaticum*

Scientific classification:

Kingdom:	Plantae
Clade:	Tracheophytes
Clade:	Angiosperms
Clade:	Eudicots
Clade:	Rosids
Order:	Myrtales
Family:	Myrtaceae
Genus:	<i>Syzygium</i>
Species:	<i>S. aromaticum</i>

Figure 1.6: (a) Clove contain active pharmaceuticals ingredients such as (b) Eugenol.

2. Cloves are the aromatic flower buds of a Myrtaceae tree that is indigenous to the Maluku Islands in Indonesia. They are also known to help lower blood sugar levels and promote the production of insulin, both of which assist control diabetes. Eugenol administration significantly increased GLUT4 translocation and AMPK phosphorylation in skeletal muscle, which enhanced glucose absorption. In C2C12 myotube cells, eugenol was found to increase intracellular Ca²⁺ levels via the transient receptor potential vanilloid channel 1 (TRPV1) gene. The phosphorylation of AMPK proteins was affected by the stimulation of TRPV1, which in turn activated calmodulin-dependent protein kinase-2 (CaMKK2). To summarize, eugenol could be a helpful nutraceutical for minimizing muscle deficiencies brought on by elevated glucose levels. This could be explained by its capacity to mediate the effects on muscle tissue of inflammation and glucose absorption.

2. DRUG PROFILE

Table 2.1: Drug profile of Diosgenin

Name of drug	Diosgenin
CAS registry no.	<u>512-04-9</u>
Chemical Structure	
IUPAC name	(25R)-Spirost-5-en-3 β -ol
Molecular Formula	C ₂₇ H ₄₂ O ₃
Molecular Weight	414.630 g·mol ⁻¹
Drug classes	Biological Agents - Plant-Derived
Solubility	The solubility of diosgenin in methanol, ethanol (95%), isopropanol, acetone, acetic ether, were measured at temperatures from (295.15 to 330.15) K water solubility at <1g/L (25 °C) OR 298.15 K

2.1. Mechanism of action Diosgenin: β -cell renewal and insulin secretion stimulation are among the processes. Additionally, Diosgenin saponin, which has antioxidative properties and plays a crucial role in treating the diabetic state through multiple mechanisms, such as β -cell renewal and insulin secretion stimulation, is believed to be the main bioactive component of fenugreek. Diosgenin also increases the amounts of peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor- γ (PPAR- γ) and CCAAT/enhancer-binding protein (C/EBP δ) mRNA transcription (10,12).

Additional components of fenugreek include the amino acid 4-hydroxyisoleucine, which increases insulin secretion and lowers levels of total cholesterol, plasma triglycerides, and insulin.

2.2 Absorption: Based on early studies with Diosgenin, the drug was shown to be readily absorbed orally in humans.

2.3 Distribution: At therapeutic concentrations, binds extensively to plasma proteins and albumin.

2.4 metabolism: occurs in the liver, where it undergoes enterohepatic recirculation.

2.5. Excretion: Diosgenin and its metabolites are excreted primarily through feces.

Table 2.2: Drug profile of Eugenol

Name of drug	Eugenol
CAS registry no.	<u>97-53-0</u>
Chemical structure	
IUPAC name	2-Methoxy-4-(prop-2-en-1-yl) phenol
Molecular Formula	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₂
Molecular weight	164.204 g·mol ⁻¹
Drug classes	Biological Agents - Plant-Derived Allergens
Solubility	It is moderately soluble in water, 2460 mg/L at 25 °C Miscible with alcohol, chloroform, ether, oils; one mL dissolves in 2 mL 70%alcohol; soluble in glacial acetic acid, in aqueous fixed alkali hydroxide solutions and also Soluble in ether, most fixed oils.
Log P	2.49

2.6. Mechanism of action Eugenol: Eugenol administration significantly increased GLUT4 translocation and AMPK phosphorylation in skeletal muscle, which enhanced glucose absorption. In C2C12 myotube cells, eugenol was found to increase intracellular Ca²⁺ levels via the transient receptor potential vanilloid channel 1 (TRPV1) gene. The phosphorylation of AMPK proteins was affected by the stimulation of TRPV1, which in turn activated calmodulin-dependent protein kinase-2 (CaMKK2). To summarize, eugenol could be a helpful nutraceutical for minimizing muscle deficiencies brought on by elevated glucose levels. This could be explained by its capacity to mediate the effects on muscle tissue of inflammation and glucose absorption.

2.7. Absorption: Based on early studies with Eugenol, the drug was shown to be readily absorbed orally in humans.

2.8. Distribution: Eugenol result in rapid distribution to all organs.

2.9. Metabolism: At therapeutic concentrations, Eugenol metabolism occurs in the liver.

2.10. Excretion: Eugenol and its metabolites are excreted primarily through feces and excreted in the urine within 24 hours and the urine contained conjugates of eugenol.

3. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

3.1. Literature Review Related to Diseases:

1. Freeman R et al. (2014) Autonomic neuropathy in diabetes A collection of conditions known as diabetic autonomic neuropathy are brought on by dysfunctions of the sympathetic and parasympathetic neural systems. Exercise intolerance, orthostatic tachycardia or bradycardia, and widespread weakness are all possible symptoms of cardiac autonomic neuropathy (CAN). Gastroparesis, another name for gastrointestinal autonomic dysfunction, is characterized by symptoms such as postprandial vomiting, bloating, early satiety with low appetite, and brittle diabetes, or diabetes that is difficult to control. Additionally, dysphagia (difficulty swallowing solid foods) and acid reflux-related discomfort might be signs of oesophageal dysfunction. Urogenital autonomic neuropathy (sometimes called diabetic cystopathy) manifests as bladder dysfunction, which can vary from urgency to hesitancy and retention of urine. Another typical sign of urogenital autonomic neuropathy is sexual dysfunction. Impotence, decreased libido, and abnormal ejaculation are the signs of sexual dysfunction in males; pain during sexual intercourse, inadequate lubrication, and decreased desire are the signs of sexual dysfunction in women. The symptoms of sudomotor autonomic dysfunction include gustatory sweating and dry skin, or anhidrosis. The particular subtype of diabetic autonomic neuropathy determines how it should be treated. While addressing all metabolic risk factors is advised for type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), optimizing glucose control early in the course of type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM) is advised to prevent or delay.^[49]

2. Pop-Busui R. et al. (2017) End-organ damage results from diabetes's effects on the central nervous system, which include behavioral abnormalities, autonomic dysfunctions, altered neuroendocrine activities, and changes in neurotransmitters. The onset of DN and degeneration is attributed to several processes, such as polyol, hexosamine, protein kinase C, advanced glycation, poly (ADP-ribose) polymerase, oxidative stress, and inflammation. Diabetic peripheral neuropathy (DPN), sometimes referred to as diabetic neuropathy (DN) or peripheral nerve dysfunction, impacts organs including the kidney, liver, heart, eyes, etc. which the autonomic nervous system stimulates. Over half of all diabetics have DN, which is usually accompanied with weak foot muscles and a lack of sensation in the feet, making walking challenging.⁵⁰

3. Demir S. & Nawroth P.P et al (2021) In individuals with diabetic polyneuropathy, the discovery of NGF—the first neurotrophic factor—was linked to neuronal degeneration. Pro-NGF, the precursor of NGF, and NGF itself are essential for the growth, differentiation, maintenance, and durability of neurons. NGF is essential for both lipid metabolism and neuronal recovery, which are the building blocks for the development of retinopathy, neuropathy, and cognitive impairment. NGF is therefore assumed to be linked to complications from diabetes. Insulin secretion is regulated by NGF and its tyrosine kinase A receptor (TrkA), which are expressed in pancreatic β cells. A study conducted in mouse islets revealed that elevated glucose levels can enhance NGF production, hence stimulating insulin release following glucose stimulation and activating the TrkA receptors on β -cells. Moreover, NGF is essential for regulating secretion of insulin levels. Apart from their anatomical resemblance, pancreatic β cells secrete and generate both insulin and NGF.⁵¹

4. von Hehn et al. (2012) (Pain brought on by a somatosensory nervous system injury or illness is known as neuropathic pain. Neuropathy affects about 30 to 50 percent of diabetic neuropathy patients. The most common type of neuropathic pain is spontaneous (i.e., not triggered by stimuli) burning sensation in the feet. Other positive sensory symptoms that patients may describe include paresthesias and brush-evoked allodynia, which is the induction of pain in response to a normally non-noxious stimulus. Patients sometimes lament the paradox of having always aching but touch-insensitive feet when experiencing these good sensory experiences, which are frequently accompanied by sensory loss. It is unclear why some patients with diabetic neuropathy experience neuropathic pain while others do not. However, this likely reflects a complex interaction of vulnerabilities, including genetics, the somatosensory nervous system, and psychological factors in response to stressors like the severity of the neuropathy and the metabolic dysfunction of diabetes. 52

3.2. Literature Review Related to Drugs:

1. Jung DH et al. (2010) Diosgenin is an extract of steroidal saponin found in several plants, such as species of *Dioscorea* and *Solanum*. Diosgenin has been shown to have a variety of pharmacological actions, such as anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant, and anti-cancer effects, according to mounting data ^[53]. Furthermore, diosgenin has been shown to have neuroprotective properties. Diosgenin's function in neuropathic pain is still unknown, though.

2. Kang TH et al. (2011) Diosgenin's anti-inflammatory, antilipoperoxidative, glucose-lowering, antioxidant, and hyperlipidemic properties might all be studied pharmacologically. In the current experimental models, diosgenin was also abundant in diet and had anti-diabetic properties. This study was further supported by the discovery that diosgenin protected a large number of viscus rate-limiting enzymes that are typically involved in the altered glucose metabolism associated with diabetes.^[54] Many experimental studies are certain to address the protective role of diosgenin in the treatment of diabetic related complications, despite the fact that there is a wealth of evidence suggesting that foods high in diosgenin may also be beneficial as an additional medication to treat polygenic disease and its associated complications.

3. Balasubramanian A et al. (2014) By controlling oxidative stress, eugenol can help with lipid metabolism issues brought on by a high-fat diet (HFD). Enhancing hepatic gluconeogenesis and maintaining blood glucose homeostasis have been shown by means of the Adenosine 50-monophosphate (AMP)-activated protein kinase (AMPK) signaling pathway. It also contributes to autoregulation and is frequently used as a surgical anesthetic. The transient receptor potential (TRP) signaling pathway, which primarily affects transient receptor potential V1/V4/A1 (TRPV1, TRPV4, TRPA1), is responsible for eugenol's anemia. The modulation of temperature and pain perception is facilitated by these TRP family targets. However, new research indicates that TRPV1 controls energy metabolism.⁵⁵

4. **Wang K et al. (2022)** In skeletal muscle, eugenol treatment dramatically raised AMPK phosphorylation and GLUT4 translocation, which improved glucose absorption. Eugenol was discovered to raise intracellular Ca²⁺ levels through the transient receptor potential vanilloid channel 1 (TRPV1) gene in C2C12 myotube cells. This activation of TRPV1 subsequently activated calmodulin-dependent protein kinase-2 (CaMKK2) and impacted AMPK protein phosphorylation. In conclusion, eugenol may be a useful nutraceutical in reducing muscular deficits caused by high blood sugar. This may be due to its ability to mediate the effects of inflammation and glucose absorption on the muscle. Eugenol may have similar activation or inhibitory effects as capsaicin, despite the fact that it can activate TRPV1. In the cell membrane, TRPV1 functions as an ion channel that regulates the entry and exit of Na⁺, K⁺, and Ca²⁺ ions. Neuronal signaling, metabolism, and inflammatory responses are all strongly correlated with Ca²⁺, a cellular regulatory messenger. Energy metabolism may be impacted by Ca²⁺ entry into cells because calmodulin activates downstream signaling pathways. Conversely, diabetes causes a rise in systemic inflammation, which then results in problems. It has been demonstrated that eugenol controls the body's inflammatory response by activating signaling pathways like COX-2 and NF-Kb.⁵⁶

4. RATIONAL

Rational:

The multifaceted illness known as diabetic neuropathy is typified by inflammation, oxidative stress, and malfunction in the mitochondria. Oxidative stress brought on by hyperglycemia is a major factor in the development of neuropathic problems. Due to their established anti-inflammatory and antioxidant qualities, diosgenin and eugenol are promising options for reducing diabetic neuropathy.

4.1 Anti-Inflammatory Potential: Diabetic neuropathy has been linked to a chronic inflammatory response. It has been demonstrated that diosgenin modifies inflammatory pathways by preventing the release of cytokines that promote inflammation. By inhibiting the synthesis of inflammatory mediators, eugenol also has anti-inflammatory properties. These substances working together might help lessen the neuroinflammation linked to diabetic neuropathy.

4.2 Neuroprotective Effects: In a variety of experimental models, diosgenin and eugenol have both shown neuroprotective characteristics. Eugenol has been shown to have neuroprotective benefits through its anti-apoptotic and anti-excitotoxic processes, whereas diosgenin has been shown to increase nerve growth factor (NGF) levels and support neuronal survival. Because of these qualities, they may be able to stop and perhaps reverse the damage done to neurons in diabetic neuropathy.

4.3 Experimental Evidence: Although earlier studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of diosgenin and eugenol in reducing the consequences of diabetes, little is known about how specifically these compounds affect diabetic neuropathy caused by STZ. By methodically examining the neuroprotective and ameliorative effects of diosgenin and eugenol in a rat model of diabetic neuropathy caused by STZ, this study seeks to close this gap. Due to their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, neuroprotective, and mitochondrial-preserving qualities, diosgenin and eugenol are being investigated for their potential to mitigate the consequences of STZ-induced diabetic neuropathy in rats. Thorough research on these substances could yield important information on possible treatment approaches for diabetic neuropathy.

5. AIM AND OBJECTIVES

AIM: To study the effect of Diosgenin & Eugenol against Streptozotocin – Induced Diabetic Neuropathy in Rats.

5.1. Objectives:

I: This study's main goal is to find out how Eugenol and Diosgenin protect rats from diabetic neuropathy caused by streptozotocin. Through a thorough assessment, this study seeks to clarify the possible neuroprotective.

II: Characteristics of Eugenol and Diosgenin together by evaluating its effect on the biochemical, behavioral, and histological markers related to diabetic neuropathy.

III: The goal of the research is to shed light on the therapeutic use of these organic substances and open the door to the creation of cutting-edge methods for the control and avoidance of diabetic neuropathy.

IV: Assess the impact on biochemical markers associated with neuropathy.

V: Investigate the histopathological changes in nerve tissues.

VI: Evaluate the oxidative stress status in the nervous system.

6. PRELIMINARY WORK

6.1. Procurement of drug

The active pharmaceutical ingredient Diosgenin were obtained Sigma-Aldrich & Eugenol was obtained from the Shreedha Phyto Extracts (Jaipur).

6.2. Identification of drugs

Preliminary studies and identification of Diosgenin and Eugenol were carried out by the following methods:

1. Appearance
2. Solubility determination
3. IR identification

6.2.1. Appearance

The samples of Diosgenin and Eugenol were checked for their appearance as shown in the table. 3.

Table 6.1 Appearance of drugs

Drug	Observed	Reported ^{57, 58}	Result
Diosgenin	White crystals or powder	White crystals or powder	Complies
Eugenol	Pale yellow or brownies powder	Pale yellow or brownies powder	Complies

6.3. Solubility determination

The solubility of diosgenin and eugenol was checked in different solvents by using the shake flask method as shown in the table. 4.

Table 6.2 Solubility of Diosgenin and Eugenol

Drug	Observed (n=3)	Reported^{57, 58}	Result
Diosgenin	The solubility of diosgenin in methanol, ethanol (95%), were measured at temperatures from (295.15 to 330.15) K water solubility at <1g/L (25 °C) OR 298.15 K	The solubility of diosgenin in methanol, ethanol (95%), isopropanol, acetone, acetic ether, were measured at temperatures from (295.15 to 330.15) K water solubility at <1g/L (25 °C) OR 298.15 K	Complies
Eugenol	It is moderately soluble in water, 2460 mg/L at 25 °C Miscible with alcohol,	It is moderately soluble in water, 2460 mg/L at 25 °C Miscible with alcohol, chloroform, ether, oils; one mL dissolves in 2 mL 70%alcohol; soluble in glacial acetic acid, in aqueous fixed alkali hydroxide solutions and also Soluble in ether, most fixed oils.	Complies

6.4 IR identification

FTIR spectra of Diosgenin and Eugenol were obtained using **Agilent Technologies FTIR Cary 630 with ATR sampling using Micro Lab** software. The range is from 500-3500 for Diosgenin and 1000-4000 for Eugenol.

6.4.1 FTIR OF DIOSGENIN.

Figure 6.1: Chemical structure of Diosgenin

standard

obtained

Table 6.3. Interpretation of IR spectrum of Diosgenin

Sr No.	Functional Group	Wave number (cm ⁻¹)	Standard wave number (cm ⁻¹)
1.	O-H Stretching	3280.1	3550-3200
2.	C-H Stretch	2974.4	3500-2800

6.4.2 FTIR OF EUGENOL.

Figure 6.2: Chemical structure of Eugenol

Table: 6.4 Interpretation of IR spectrum of Eugenol

Sr No.	Functional Group	Wave number (cm⁻¹)	Standard wave number (cm⁻¹)
1.	O-H Stretching	3302.4	3550-3200
2.	C-H Stretch	2922.2	3500-2800
2.	Ar C=C	1520.8	1600-1585
3.	R-O-R	1267.3	1250-1050

7. MATERIAL AND METHODS

7.1 Animals: The experiment is performed after approval of the protocol by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (IAEC) of Krishna School of Pharmacy and Research. (Protocol approval No.: KSP/IAEC/2024/03) The Experiment is conducted according to the Committee for Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals (CCSEA) guidelines.

Wistar Female rats were obtained from Zydus Research Center, Moriya, Ahmedabad. They will be kept in a conventional environment with free access to food and water and a light-dark cycle of 12 hours. The rats will undergo a 48-hour acclimation period prior to the commencement of behavioral assessments. There will be one use for each animal (n = 6 animals per group).

7.2. Chemicals: In the present study, all chemicals used were of analytical grade. Diosgenin was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich & eugenol was obtained from the Shreedha Phyto Extracts (Jaipur). The other chemicals such as Pregabalin & Metformin were obtained as a gift sample from Alembic Pharmaceuticals Ltd, Vadodara & chemicals such as Streptozotocin were obtained from SRL/Himedia (lab-Chem Corporation, (India).

7.3. Selection of dose: Oral eugenol dosages (10 mg/kg) were chosen based on Pavela's (2015)⁵⁷ oral acute toxicity trials, while diosgenin was given at a dose of 20 mg/kg. The dosage of pregabalin that was given was 10 mg/kg. Orally, a single intraperitoneal injection of streptozotocin (STZ, 55 mg/kg BW) in citrate buffer at pH (4.5) was given along with 70 mg/kg of metformin.

7.4. Experimental design:

Table 7.1 Study design

Groups	Treatment	No. of Animals
I	Normal Control (Normal Saline)	6*
II	Diabetic Control (STZ 55mg/kg, i.p.)	6*
III	Diabetic STZ (55mg/kg, i.p.) + Std Control (Metformin 70mg/kg, oral)	6*
IV	Diabetic (STZ 55mg/kg, i.p.) + Pregabalin (10mg/kg, p.o.) + Metformin (70mg/kg, p.o.)	6
V	Diabetic (STZ 55mg/kg, i.p.) + Diosgenin (20mg/kg, p.o.) + Eugenol (10mg/kg, p.o.)	6
		Total=18*+12=30

Note: Groups: I, II, and III are the common groups that are shared with our colleagues to minimize the use of the animals.

7.5. Induction of Diabetic Neuropathy:

Female Wistar rats from Groups II (diabetic control), III, IV, and V were fed a high-fat diet (HFD) along with unlimited water instead of conventional rat chow. This caused the rats to become obese, which increased the likelihood of inducing type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). Streptozotocin (55 mg/kg, i.p.) dissolved in citrate buffer (pH 4.5) was injected to induce diabetes. To verify the rats' diabetes condition, fasting blood glucose concentrations were measured on the seventh day. Using a glucometer and blood samples obtained from the tail region, the glucose level was determined. The study comprised animals whose blood glucose levels at fasting were 250 mg/dL. Single, dose of STZ-injected animals were observed for signs of disease. In order to stay hygienic and prevent infections, bedding was changed daily⁵⁸.

Figure 7.1: Streptozotocin (55 mg/kg, i.p.) dissolved in citrate buffer (pH 4.5)

Figure 7.2: Glucose level was measured using a glucometer and hyperglycemia was observed in rats for the development microvascular diseases as diabetic neuropathy.

7.5.1. Validation of Diabetic Neuropathy Rats:

After the induction of diabetes, animals were assessed for the development of diabetic neuropathy. The development of diabetic neuropathy was properly assessed in all groups by the help of Thermal Hyperalgesia –Eddy's hot plate method, Number of Writhing Responses in 10 min Cold Hyperalgesia (Acetone drop test), Mechanical Hyperalgesia (Pinprick test), Grip Strength test and Rotarod tests on 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 8th week in all groups respectively.

7.6. Body Weight, Food Consumption, and Water Intake:

Throughout the trial, the body weights of the controls and diabetic rats were recorded. To measure the rats' food and water consumption, they were given 100 g of food and 100 mL of water for twenty-four hours after they had fasted the previous night. Rats' food consumption was calculated by measuring the difference between the pre-weighed food (100 g) and the weight of the remaining food based on each rat's body weight. In addition, the amount of water eaten (the difference between the total amount of water and the amount still in the bottle) was measured based on each rat's body weight⁵⁹.

7.7. Behavioral study:

- **Thermal Hyperalgesia: Hot plate method**

For this experiment, each group's animals were housed separately on a hot plate analgesiometer (Columbus Instruments, USA) with a temperature set to 55 ± 1 °C. When the first indications of paw licking or jumping were observed, they were noted, and the index of pain threshold was derived. To prevent any harm to the animals' paws, the experiment's cutoff time was set at 10 seconds. We evaluated this study in weeks 1, 2nd, 3rd, and 4th (Kuhad and Chopra, 2009).⁶⁰

Figure 7.3: Hot plate method.

- **Writhing responses**

The acetic acid writhing method was used to measure neuropathic pain in animals across all groups. A solution of 1% v/v acetic acid produced in distilled water was administered to the animals. The rats were injected intraperitoneally (i.p.) with 1% acetic acid in a volume of approximately 0.1 ml/10g body weight 60 minutes after the doses were administered. Next, for thirty minutes, the episodes were recorded, and the number of stretching motions—such as the body's elongation, the back's extension, and the limbs' extension—was recorded. (Zhang et al., 2018).⁶¹

- **Cold hyperalgesia: acetone drop test**

The responses of rats for cold sensitivity were recorded by performing the acetone drop test method. Rats from all groups were separately kept on a mesh cage to make them adjustable to the environment. Then a fresh drop of 50 μ L acetone was applied onto the paw gently (on the mid plantar surface). A cold stimulation was generated post 2–5 s of the application of acetone and the responses observed were shaking, licking of paw, rubbing or mild paw withdraws. Such reactions were recorded as the nociceptive responses while the no responses were termed as anti-nociceptive effects. These tests were performed on week 1, week 2, week 3, and week 4 of the experiment. The tests were performed on both paws at a time interval of 5 min and the mean responses were recorded (Bennett and Xie, 1988).⁶²

- **Mechanical hyperalgesia: pinprick test**

A 90° bent gauge needle was used to touch the rat's rear paw to ensure that there was no needle puncture and that only a pick was made. All groups' reflexive withdrawal responses were noted and observed. The length of the paw withdrawal was measured in seconds, with a 20-second cutoff. The results were recorded in all groups for weeks 1, 2, 3, and 4 (Kanaan et al., 1996).⁶³

7.8. Lipid profile

The lipid profile was conducted by performing the lipid profile tests after collecting blood by retro-orbital methods on the 4th week of experimentation. Serum was separated from plasma by the help of centrifugation on Remi Industries Ltd (Mumbai, India) for 10 min at a speed of 3000 rpm. The serum was used for performing analysis like total protein, uric acid, cholesterol, Albumin, Creatinine (CRE) and Triglyceride analysis. The manufacturers of the kit were (Erba Diagnostics Ltd. India

7.9. Sample Collection and Preparation

7.9.1 Sample Collection:

Rats blood samples were obtained using the retro-orbital technique. Isoflurane was used to induce minimal discomfort in the rat during anesthesia. The retro-orbital sinus was gently punctured with a capillary tube to obtain 0.5–1 milliliters of blood. Without delay, the blood was moved into a centrifuge tube.

Figure 7.4: Sample collection via Retro-Orbital puncture.

7.9.2 Sample Preparation: For thirty minutes, the drawn blood samples were left to coagulate at room temperature. To separate the serum, the samples were centrifuged for 10 minutes at 3000 rpm. If analysis was not done right away, the serum was properly pipetted into clean tubes and stored between 2 and 8°C.

Figure 7.5: Instrument of cooling centrifuge.

7.10. Cholesterol Kit CHOD-PAP Endpoint Assay Method

7.10.1 Introduction

The current investigation used the Erba Mannheim LiquiXX Cholesterol CHOD-PAP endpoint kit to assess the cholesterol levels in various groups. The retro-orbital approach, which is effective and minimally invasive when done appropriately, is frequently employed in small animal experiments to collect blood samples. The concentrations of total cholesterol were subsequently determined by analyzing the serum samples that had been taken.

Figure 7.6: Erba Mannheim LiquiXX Cholesterol CHOD-PAP endpoint kit.

7.10.2 Principle

The first step is the specific conversion of cholesterol to cholest-4-en-3-one and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) by the enzyme cholesterol oxidase (CHOD). The subsequent reaction involving hydrogen peroxide, phenol, and 4-aminoantipyrine is catalyzed by the enzyme peroxidase (PAP), which results in the creation of a quinoneimine dye complex. The amount of cholesterol present in the sample is directly correlated with the intensity of this colored complex. The amount of cholesterol in the sample can be precisely measured by utilizing a semiauto analyzer to measure the color's absorbance at a particular wavelength.

Table 7.2 Cholesterol standard solution Cholesterol CHOD-PAP Endpoint Assay Method

Cholesterol standard	200mg/dl
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7.10.3 Instruments

- i. Semiauto autoanalyzer or biochemistry analyzer compatible with CHOD-PAP method
- ii. Micropipettes and tips
- iii. Test tubes or cuvettes
- iv. Cooling centrifuge

Figure 7.7: Instrument of Biochemistry Analyzer

Figure 7.8: Sample Preparation for Cholesterol standard solution Cholesterol CHOD-PAP Endpoint Assay Method.

7.10.4 Assay Procedure

1. Calibration:

2. The cholesterol standard solution included in the kit was used for calibration. Plotting absorbance data against known cholesterol concentrations resulted in the creation of a calibration curve.

3. Assay Protocol:

- ✓ 10 μ L of each serum sample or standard was pipetted into separate test tubes or cuvettes.
- ✓ 1 mL of the reagent mixture (buffer + enzyme) was added to each tube.
- ✓ The tubes were mixed thoroughly and incubated at 37°C for 10 minutes.
- ✓ The absorbance of the test and standard was read against the reagent blank.

7.10.5 Calculation

$$\text{Cholesterol mg/dl} = \text{abs of test} / \text{abs of standard} * \text{concentration of std mg/dl}$$

The cholesterol concentration in each sample was determined using the calibration curve.

7.11. Total protein LIQUIXX Biuret method, Endpoint Assay

7.11.1 Introduction

outlined the importance of the total protein kit from Erba LIQUIXX Company for biochemical analysis. the significance of total protein level measurements for research and diagnostic applications in a variety of biological samples.

Figure 7.9: Erba Mannheim LiquiXX Total Protein Biuret Reagent Kit.

7.11.2 Principle

outlined the basic idea of the biuret technique, which depended on the formation of a colored complex by the interaction of peptide bonds with copper ions. explained how the amount of proteins present in the sample exactly correlated with the color intensity that was created.

7.11.3 Sample and Reagent Handling

- ✓ Labelled test tubes or cuvettes for blank, standard, and sample.
- ✓ Pipetted a specific volume (usually 1 ml) of the Biuret Reagent into each test tube or cuvette.
- ✓ The Erba LIQUIXX total protein provided ready-to-use reagents. If dilution was necessary, instructions were followed precisely.
- **Blank Preparation:**
Added a specified volume (typically around 10 μ l) of distilled water to the blank tube or cuvette.
- **Standard Preparation:**
Added the specified volume (typically around 10 μ l) of the standard solution to the standard tube or cuvette.
- **Sample Preparation:**
Added the specified volume (typically around 10 μ l) of the sample to the sample tube or cuvette.

- **Standards and Controls:**
 - i. Total protein standard solution
 - ii. Quality control sera

Table 7.3 Standard for Total protein Kit Biuret method, Endpoint Assay Kit

Total protein standard	6.0 g/dl
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7.11.4 Assay Procedure

Reagent Addition: Within each tube holding the samples, controls, and standards, a predetermined volume of the produced Biuret Reagent was added. To guarantee homogeneity, the ingredients were well combined.

7.11.5 Calculation

Protein Concentration g/dl = Absorbance of test/ Absorbance of standard *
concentration of standard g/dl

7.12. Uric Acid Kit with the Uricase Trinder Endpoint Method

7.12.1 Introduction

The Uricase Trinder Endpoint Method is used by the Erba LIQUIXX Uric Acid Kit to quantitatively detect the amount of uric acid present in serum or plasma. This enzymatic procedure is predicated on uricase oxidizing uric acid to produce hydrogen peroxide and allantoin, which are then combined in a colorimetric reaction with a chromogen to form a colored molecule. The content of uric acid is directly correlated with the color intensity, which is measured at 510 nm.

Figure 7.10: Erba Mannheim LiquiXX Uric acid Kit with the Uricase Trinder Endpoint Method.

7.12.2 Principle

Uricase Reaction: The uricase enzyme oxidizes uric acid to yield hydrogen peroxide and allantoin. Trinder Reaction: In the presence of peroxidase, a chromogen and the hydrogen peroxide created in the first reaction combine to make a colored compound.

7.12.3 Methodology

The absorbance of the colored substance at 510 nm was used to calculate the concentration of uric acid. The amount of uric acid in the sample is determined by comparing the absorbance to a standard curve.

Table 7.4 Standards for Uric Acid Kit with the Uricase Trinder Endpoint Method

Uric acid standard	6.0 mg/dl
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7.12.4 Calculation

Uric acid Concentration mg/dl = Absorbance of test/ Absorbance of standard * concentration of standard mg/dl

7.13. Albumin Kit BCG Dey, end point method

7.13.1 Introduction

A diagnostic reagent kit for quantifying albumin in serum was the Erba LIQUIXX Albumin Kit BCG. The primary protein in human blood plasma, albumin, is essential for osmotic pressure regulation, material transportation, and a number of metabolic activities.

Figure 7.11: Erba Mannheim Albumin Kit BCG Dey, end point method.

7.13.2 Principle

The Erba LIQUIXX Albumin Kit BCG technique depended on the greenish-colored complex that was formed between albumin and the acidic dye Bromocresol Green (BCG). The amount of albumin present was directly associated with the intensity of the resultant hue. A calibration curve was utilized to ascertain the albumin concentrations, and measurements were predicated on absorbance measurements at a particular wavelength.

7.13.3 Methodology

The BCG reagent and serum samples were combined, the mixtures were incubated, and the absorbance of the resultant complexes was measured. Sample preparation, reagent mixing, reaction start-up, and spectrophotometric analysis were among the steps. The measurements of absorbance were compared to a standard curve made using known albumin concentrations.

7.13.4 Albumin standard

Table 7.5 Standard Reagent Composition for Albumin BCG Endpoint method

Albumin standard	3.6 g/dl
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7.13.5 Assay procedure

After a minute of incubation at 37°C, the samples were thoroughly mixed, and the absorbance of the standard and each test was measured at 630 nm against the reagent blank.

7.13.6 Calculation

Albumin Concentration g/dl = Absorbance of test/ Absorbance of standard * concentration of standard g/dl

7.14. Triglyceride GPO-tinder method endpoint

7.14.1 Introduction

A colorimetric test called the Erba Mannheim LiquiXX Triglycerides GPO-PAP method is used to measure the amount of triglycerides in serum or plasma quantitatively. High levels of triglycerides, a type of lipid, can be a sign of several metabolic conditions, such as pancreatitis and cardiovascular disease. This technique provides a dependable and accurate assessment by using the enzymatic hydrolysis of triglycerides followed by a colorimetric detection.

Figure 7.12: Erba Mannheim LiquiXX Triglycerides GPO-PAP method kit

7.14.2 Principle

The process is based on lipase's enzymatic hydrolysis of triglycerides, which yields free fatty acids and glycerol. Next, glycerol kinase phosphorylates the glycerol to become glycerol-3-phosphate. Glycerol-3-phosphate oxidase next oxidizes the glycerol to form hydrogen peroxide. Lastly, red quinoneimine dye is created when hydrogen peroxide, p-chlorophenol, and 4-aminophenazone combine catalytically with peroxidase. Photometric measurement at 500 nm can be used to determine the intensity of color produced, which is directly proportional to the triglyceride concentration in the sample.

7.14.3 Methodology

A multi-step enzymatic reaction sequence is used in this method to generate a chromogenic molecule. The triglyceride concentration is found by mixing the sample with the reagents and measuring the absorbance of the resultant solution.

7.14.4 Assay procedure

The materials were thoroughly mixed and then incubated at 37°C for 10 minutes. Each test's absorbance was measured at 546/670 nm in comparison to the reagent blank.

7.14.5 Calculation

Triglyceride Concentration mg/dl = Absorbance of test/ Absorbance of standard * concentration of standard mg/dl

7.15. Determination of Percent Glycated Hemoglobin (%HbA1c)

The sample was prepared using a conventional hemolysate method, which involved centrifuging heparinized blood at 2,000 to 2,000 Xg and twice washing the cells in 0.9 percent saline.⁶⁵ An equivalent volume of water was used to lyse the packed cells, and 0.4 liter of toluene was used to extract the cells over night. Shortly before analysis, the aqueous phase was centrifuged for 30 minutes at 20,000Xg.

The HPLC method, an invitro assay for the quantitative detection of glycosylated Hb by HPLC, BIO-RAD10, Germany, was used to measure the level of hemoglobin A1c.

Figure 7.13: HPLC, BIO-RAD10, GERMANY.

7.16. Serum Insulin: Extraction of insulin that is free. An automatic syringe was used to add 1 ml of a cold 25% (w/w) polyethylene glycol solution to 1 ml of plasma that had been chilled in an ice water bath. The mixture was then quickly vortically mixed for one minute and centrifuged at 3,000 r.p.m. for 45 minutes in a refrigerated centrifuge. In 411-roche, USA, the supernatant was employed for the radioimmunoassay.

Figure 7.14: The immunoassay analyzer cobas e 411 2nd generation platform of ECL technology.

7.16.1 Biochemical Analysis

Getting Ready for Brain Homogenate The rats were immediately sacrificed by cervical decapitation following the behavioral tests, and the brains were promptly removed and allowed to solidify for ten minutes in boxes containing frozen saline. To create the 10% homogenate, the brain was placed into a graduated cylinder and PBS (pH 7.4) was added afterward. Every tube was centrifuged for 15 minutes at 4° C at 10,000 rpm/min, and the supernatant was taken out for biochemical examinations.

7.16. Assessment of Oxidative Stress in Brain Tissue

7.17. SOD (Superoxide Dismutase) enzyme assays using spectrophotometric measurements. (74)

Materials Needed:

1. Spectrophotometer capable of measuring absorbance at 480 nm and 540 nm
2. Tissue homogenate containing the enzyme of interest (SOD)
3. Carbonate buffer (pH 10.2, typically 50 mM)
4. EDTA solution (typically 1 mM)
5. Distilled water
6. Superoxide anion generator (e.g., epinephrine)
7. Standard SOD solutions of known activity (5-160 units/ml)

Superoxide Dismutase (SOD) enzyme activity can be measured using spectrophotometric test. First, prepare a tissue homogenate and centrifuge to generate a supernatant. To adjust for background levels, prepare a blank in a clean cuvette with distilled water and measure the absorbance at 540 nm. To create a standard curve later, prepare a series of standard SOD solutions with known activity (usually ranging from 5 to 160 units/ml). To stabilize pH and avoid metal-catalyzed reactions, combine the tissue homogenate supernatant with carbonate buffer (pH 10.2) and EDTA for each sample, including standards and unknowns. To initiate the process, add a superoxide anion generator, such as epinephrine. Measure the initial absorbance at 480 nm right away to determine the rate at which superoxide radicals are produced. Measure the final absorbance at 480 nm after adding the enzyme sample to start the reaction and letting it incubate for a predetermined amount of time (usually 5–20 minutes). Determine the SOD activity in the unknown samples by calculating the absorbance values, correcting for dilution effects, and utilizing the standard curve. Through the use of spectrophotometric analysis, this technology guarantees the systematic measurement of SOD activity, yielding accurate information on the antioxidant capacity of the enzyme in the tissue homogenate samples under investigation.

Standard Concentration (units/ml)	Volume of Stock SOD Solution (ml)	Volume of Dilution (ml)	of Buffer	Total Volume (ml)
5	0.005	0.995		1
10	0.01	0.99		1
20	0.02	0.98		1
40	0.04	0.96		1
80	0.08	0.92		1
160	0.16	0.84		1

In order to gather information for the Superoxide Dismutase (SOD) enzyme activity spectrophotometric assay, begin by measuring the absorbance at 540 nm to create a baseline absorbance using a blank that contains distilled water. This will account for any background absorbance. Next, for every prepared standard SOD solution with known activity (usually ranging from 5 to 160 units/ml), measure the initial absorbance at 480 nm. When creating a standard curve, these initial absorbance data are used as a point of reference. To stabilize pH and avoid metal-catalyzed reactions, combine the tissue homogenate supernatant with carbonate buffer (pH 10.2) and EDTA for each sample, including standards and unknowns. To start the process, add a superoxide anion generator, such as epinephrine, and measure the absorbance at 480 nm right away to determine the rate at which superoxide radicals are produced. Allow the enzyme to scavenge the superoxide radicals by letting it incubate for a predetermined amount of time (typically 5–20 minutes) after adding the enzyme sample. To find the leftover superoxide levels, measure the absorbance at 480 nm at the end of the incubation period. To account for any non-enzymatic reactions, subtract the initial absorbance from the final absorbance for each sample and modify the resultant value based on the corresponding blank readings. This yields the corrected absorbance. To find the associated SOD activity in units/ml or units/mg protein, interpolate the corrected absorbance of each sample using the standard curve that was previously created using the absorbance values of the standard solutions. To ensure accuracy and clarity in recording the absorbance readings, computations, and final SOD activity results for each sample, record and arrange all data in a methodical manner. This all-encompassing method guarantees accurate detection and interpretation of SOD enzyme activity in the examined tissue homogenates, offering insightful information about their antioxidant potential.

To conduct a spectrophotometric assay for Glutathione (GSH) enzyme activity, (69,70,71)

In order to ensure reliable measurement and interpretation of GSH levels in biological samples, the process consists of multiple methodical steps. To begin, tissue homogenates from the retinal tissues of Wistar rats are made, and these are then centrifuged to produce a supernatant that contains soluble proteins, such as GSH. To create baseline readings for background correction, distilled water is used to generate a blank solution that is prepared in clean cuvettes or microplate wells. The blank solution's absorbance is measured at a certain wavelength, usually around 412 nm.

In order to preserve enzyme activity and stable pH, a series of GSH standards with established concentrations—typically ranging from 0 to 100 μM —are then generated using the proper buffer solutions. In order to create a standard curve, which is essential for determining the amount of GSH present in unknown samples, these standards are used as references. Carbonate buffer (pH 7.4) and DTNB (5,5'-dithiobis-2-nitrobenzoic acid), a reagent that particularly reacts with GSH, are combined with each sample—both standards and experimental specimens—in the cuvette to start the reaction. The reaction kinetics are captured by measuring the initial absorbance right away.

After oxidized glutathione (GSSG) is converted to reduced glutathione (GSH) with the help of glutathione reductase and NADPH, the samples are incubated at a predetermined temperature (usually 25°C), and absorbance is measured during a predetermined amount of time (e.g., 3 minutes). The absorbance change (ΔA) for every sample and standard is determined by recording and utilizing the final absorbance values. The concentration of GSH in the samples can be precisely calculated by consulting the standard curve, taking into consideration sample quantities and dilution factors.

In order to ensure reproducibility, quality control procedures include making sure all measurements fall within the linear range of the standard curve and doing duplicate or triple measurements for each sample. Then, statistical analysis is carried out using t-tests or ANOVA to compare GSH concentrations between various experimental

groups (treated vs. untreated, diabetic retinopathy vs. normal controls, etc.). Together, these actions offer insights into the tissues' antioxidant capacities and aid in evaluating the efficacy of treatments meant to modify GSH levels in situations involving oxidative stress.

Table 7.6 Preparation of GSH Standards with Concentrations, Ranges, and Volumes:

GSH Standard Concentration (μM)	Range for Spectrophotometric Assay (μM)	Volume of GSH Standard (μL) Range	Volume of Buffer (μL) Range	Total Volume (μL) Range
0	0	0	0-100	100
10	5-15	5-15	85-95	100
20	15-25	15-25	75-85	100
30	25-35	25-35	65-75	100
40	35-45	35-45	55-65	100
50	45-55	45-55	45-55	100
60	55-65	55-65	35-45	100
70	65-75	65-75	25-35	100
80	75-85	75-85	15-25	100
90	85-95	85-95	5-15	100
100	95-105	95-105	0-10	100

- **Note:** For each standard, adjust the quantities of GSH standard and buffer within the given limits to obtain the required concentrations. For every normal preparation, the total volume stays at 100 μL . These ranges offer versatility in creating GSH standards appropriate for spectrophotometric measurements, guaranteeing precise assessment of GSH levels in test specimens. Modify in accordance with certain experimental specifications or assay sensitivity.

Estimation of Malondialdehyde ⁽⁶⁶⁻⁶⁸⁾

Thiobarbituric Acid Reactive Substances.

Assay: Principle The method estimates Malondialdehyde (MDA), a product of the lipid peroxidation process (MDA; nM/mg protein) employing the Ohkawa et al. method. One molecule of MDA reacts with two molecules of thiobarbituric acid (TBA) under mildly acidic conditions to form a pink-colored chromogen, whose intensity is measured colorimetrically at 532 nm.

Reagents: 1. Thiobarbituric acid (0.67% in Tris-hydrochloride, pH 7): use 100 ml of Tris hydrochloride buffer pH 7 to dissolve 0.67 gm of thiobarbituric acid (or 0.375%).
2. Distilled water should be used to dissolve 10 grams of trichloroacetic acid (10%).

Procedure: Assemble the test and blank solutions as indicated below: No answer at all:
To 1 milliliter of distilled water, add 2 milliliter of 10% trichloroacetic acid. Let it cool for 15 minutes, then centrifuge it for 10 minutes at 3000 rpm. Take 2 milliliter of the supernatant and add 2 milliliter of thiobarbituric acid (0.67% in Tris hydrochloride, pH 7).

Test Solution: To 1 milliliter of homogenate, add 2 milliliters of 10% trichloroacetic acid, and let it cool for 15 minutes. Centrifugation is used to separate the precipitates, and the supernatant is then combined with 2 milliliters of thiobarbituric acid (0.67% in tris-hydrochloride, pH 7) After 10 minutes of continuous boiling in a water bath at 95 oC (or 80 oC for 40 minutes), the solution is chilled in ice for five minutes. Using a spectrophotometer, measure the test's absorbance at 535 nm in relation to the blank. The generation of malonaldehyde is used to express the results.

7.21. Estimation of Catalase (75,76)

The Aeb technique is used to measure the activity of catalase. 1.9 ml of 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) was added to 0.1 ml of supernatant. The addition of 1.0 ml of freshly made 30 mM H₂O₂ starts the reaction. Using spectrophotometry, one may determine the rate of H₂O₂ breakdown based on variations in absorbance at 240 nm. For three minutes, the rate at which the absorbance decreased was measured at 240 nm. The protein's $\mu\text{mol}/\text{mg}$ was used to express the results.

7.22. INFLAMMATORY BIOMARKERS

7.22.1 CRP T-LTX Method, Erba Mannheim Liquixx CRP Kit

Introduction

A diagnostic test called the Erba Mannheim Liquixx CRP T-LTX method was used to determine the amount of C-reactive protein (CRP) in human serum or plasma quantitatively using a biochemistry analyzer. The liver produces CRP, an acute-phase protein, in reaction to inflammation, infection, or tissue damage. Increased CRP levels were suggestive of inflammatory conditions, which helped with the diagnosis and treatment of a number of illnesses, such as cardiovascular diseases, chronic inflammatory diseases, and bacterial infections.

Figure 7.15: Inflammatory biomarkers CRP by T-LTX Method (Kit)

7.22.2 Principle

Using this method, latex particles coated with CRP-specific antibodies were agglutinated. These latex particles were combined with the CRP sample, which sparked an antigen-antibody response that resulted in the development of immunological complexes. The degree of agglutination was determined turbidimetrically at a particular wavelength and was directly proportional to the CRP levels in the sample. As a result, there was a correlation between the rise in turbidity and the CRP level, which could be measured with a conventional calibration curve.

7.22.3 Assay Procedure

Preparation

All reagents and samples were allowed to reach room temperature.

The CRP Latex Reagent was mixed thoroughly before use.

Calibration

Ten milliliters of distilled water were used to reconstitute the CRP calibrator. After a gentle mixing, it was allowed to sit at room temperature for ten minutes.

LABCARE CK-MB Kit

Introduction:

The enzyme known as CK-MB is created when two subunits from muscle (M) and nerve cells (B) bind together. CK-MB is typically found in serum at low concentrations; it rises following an acute myocardial infarction and then falls to normal levels. Additionally, there is a rare increase in skeletal muscle injury. 5.6. A clinical diagnosis should take into account both clinical and additional laboratory evidence, rather than being based solely on a test result.

Figure 7.16: biomarkers CK-MB Method (Kit)

PRINCIPLE

In this process, the activity of creatine kinase (CK) is measured while an antibody against the CK-M monomer is present. An anti-CK-M antibody in the reagent totally inhibits the CK-M portions of the CK MM and the CK-MB in the sample. Next comes the CK-8 fraction (NAC act.) method's activity. The activity of CK-MB is

CK-B activity is multiplied by CK using the CK (NAC act.) technique to determine the obtained wo.

Table 7.7 Reference values:

Serum (37 °C)	0-24 U/L
Serum (30 °C)	0-14 U/L

Table 7.8 Manual Assay Procedure:

Working Reagent	1000 µL
Incubate at Assay temperature for 1 min and add.	
Sample	50 µL

Mix well and after 5 min measure the change in absorbance. Read the initial absorbance and start timer simultaneously, read again after every 60 seconds for 5 minutes. Calculate & Almin.

CALCULATION

$$U/l CKBA = \Delta A/min. \times 6752$$

7.23. Histopathological Examination of Brain, sciatic nerves, liver and Pancreas:

Brain, sciatic nerve, liver, and pancreatic tissue were preserved in 10% buffered formalin solution for histological examinations. The brain, sciatic nerves, liver, and pancreatic tissues were fixed in 10% buffered formalin solution, thinly sliced, dried, and then embedded in paraffin. The pancreas, sciatic nerves, and isolated brain were cut into 5-millimeter pieces, preserved for three days in a 10% neutral formalin solution, and then rinsed under running water for roughly twelve hours. Dehydration using alcohol at progressively higher strengths (70, 80, and 90%) for 12 hours each came next. Absolute alcohol was used for the final dehydration, with three changes made every twelve minutes. Xylene was used for cleaning, and changes were made every 15 to 20 minutes. The pieces were cleaned and then placed in an automatic tissue processing device for paraffin infiltration. The formalin was entirely removed from the pieces by washing them under running water. From each sample, at least four cross-sections with a thickness of 3-5 µm were cut, and they were then stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E). With DPX, tissue slices were mounted.

Figure 7.17: Observation of visible changes on Organs A. Kidney B. Spleen C. Pancreas D. Heart

Figure 7.18: histological organs analyses, (a) pancreas, (b) sciatic nerves and (c) brain

7.12. Statistical Analysis

GraphPad Prism software was used to exhibit data as mean \pm standard error mean (SEM). The Data were shown as $x \pm$ SEM. Statistical analysis was performed by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Brown-Forsythe test and Bartlett's multiple comparison test.

8. Blood Glucose:

Table 8.1 Effect of diosgenin & eugenol on fasting blood sugar level during the course of anti-diabetic study model.

Day's	Normal Control						Stz +Dc						Stz+Met						Stz+Pre						Stz+D+E					
DAY 0	108	110	112	105	109	106	200	202	210	216	220	222	240	245	248	242	241	243	244	246	240	247	241	245	255	284	321	348	390	530
DAY 2	134	135	109	111	109	111	203	198	201	233	246	241	240	244	247	242	240	243	243	245	240	246	240	244	254	284	320	347	389	529
DAY 7	111	115	110	112	110	108	208	200	209	234	248	247	220	224	227	222	220	223	223	225	220	266	220	224	239	268	305	328	370	450
DAY 14	109	108	112	111	110	108	213	204	208	234	248	247	190	194	197	192	190	193	193	195	190	196	190	194	199	228	245	270	292	340
DAY 21	110	110	107	105	101	105	243	239	240	277	276	270	150	154	157	152	150	153	148	150	145	151	145	149	159	198	170	195	200	220
DAY 28	103	107	106	105	101	103	259	263	267	290	299	287	95	99	102	97	95	98	98	100	95	101	95	99	109	107	91	115	121	105

Effect of Diosgenin & eugenol, and their combination on blood glucose level. A $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. Significance is represented as *** $p < 0.001$; a—normal control versus daibetic control corresponding to the same day, b—daibetic control versus treatment groups corresponding to same day.

8.1. Body weight:

Table 8.2 Effect of diosgenin & eugenol on body weight of anti-diabetic study model.

Day's	Normal Control						Stz +Met						Stz+Met						Stz+Pre						Stz D+E					
DAY 0	250	252	260	255	258	255	255	265	250	250	252	260	255	265	250	250	252	260	195	198	191	195	192	192	195	195	192	192	191	192
DAY 2	270	260	269	265	270	265	198	190	192	195	196	192	198	190	192	195	196	192	202	208	206	205	202	200	205	200	200	207	200	205
DAY 7	272	265	262	267	265	267	200	195	197	199	200	196	200	195	197	199	200	196	212	220	226	220	215	220	220	215	220	226	220	215
DAY 14	270	268	271	268	266	268	202	198	202	201	202	200	202	198	202	201	202	200	258	260	246	260	255	250	245	247	244	245	243	243
DAY 21	270	265	270	268	266	268	205	200	206	202	204	205	205	200	206	202	204	205	266	268	256	268	265	260	251	258	255	251	257	255
DAY 28	272	270	270	270	264	270	208	202	210	205	207	208	208	202	210	205	207	208	272	275	266	275	270	268	270	275	272	270	275	273

Effect of Diosgenin, eugenol, and their combination on changes in the body weight of experimental rats. A $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. Significance is represented as * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$; a—normal control versus diabetic control corresponding to the same day, b—diabetic control versus treatment groups corresponding to same day.

8.2 a. Water Intake:

Table 8.3 Effect of diosgenin & eugenol on water Intake of anti-diabetic study model.

Day's	Normal Control						Stz +Met						Stz+Met						Stz+Pre						StzDiosgenin+Eugenol					
DAY 0	25	28	25	25	28	25	28	28	25	30	29	30	69	70	70	77	75	74	60	65	68	70	65	62	60	60	62	68	70	63
DAY 2	30	28	30	29	28	30	35	38	32	38	37	37	65	70	68	77	75	72	57	63	66	67	63	60	57	57	59	65	67	60
DAY 7	28	30	25	26	30	28	45	48	42	49	48	47	62	67	66	74	72	69	51	58	60	61	58	56	51	50	54	59	61	54
DAY 14	30	26	28	28	25	26	53	59	52	61	60	58	48	50	46	49	48	59	43	37	32	35	46	47	43	43	45	51	53	46
DAY 21	27	28	30	30	24	28	65	70	63	77	68	68	38	42	36	39	40	49	33	27	24	27	26	25	33	33	35	41	43	36
DAY 28	30	30	28	28	29	30	75	77	72	79	70	75	26	32	28	30	32	30	29	32	28	32	30	30	29	23	25	31	33	26

Effect of Diosgenin & eugenol, and their combination on (a) **water Intake**. A $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. Significance is represented as * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, and *** $p < 0.001$; a—normal control versus diabetic control corresponding to the same day, b—diabetic control versus treatment groups corresponding to same day.

8.2 b. Food Intake:

Table 8.4 Effect of diosgenin & eugenol on food Intake of anti-diabetic study model.

Day's	Normal Control						Stz +Met						Stz+Met						Stz+Pre						StzDiosgenin+Eugenol					
DAY 0	52	44	51	46	50	44	30	35	32	35	30	38	25	22	24	20	26	20	22	26	18	26	24	25	22	20	23	18	25	19
DAY 2	50	49	45	50	48	47	29	32	31	32	29	37	27	22	25	22	25	22	23	26	20	27	24	26	23	25	28	20	25	21
DAY 7	45	50	48	48	49	49	24	27	27	27	24	34	31	26	29	26	29	26	28	31	25	32	28	31	28	29	32	25	29	26
DAY 14	48	52	50	48	51	50	20	22	22	22	20	30	36	31	34	31	34	31	32	35	29	36	33	35	32	34	37	29	34	30
DAY 21	48	45	52	50	50	52	25	24	24	24	25	26	40	35	39	36	39	36	37	40	34	41	28	40	37	42	45	34	39	35
DAY 28	50	48	52	51	52	52	21	20	20	20	21	22	48	43	47	41	47	41	45	48	42	49	46	48	45	47	48	42	46	43

Effect of Diosgenin & eugenol, and their combination on **(b) food intake**. A $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. Significance is represented as * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, and *** $p < 0.001$; a—normal control versus diabetic control corresponding to the same day, b— diabetic control versus treatment groups corresponding to same day.

8.3. Behavioral study

8.3.1 Eddy's hot plate method

Table 8.5 The impact of chlorogenic acid on Thermal Hyperalgesia: evaluating diabetic neuropathy in Wistar albino rats using Eddy's hot plate test.

S. No.	Treatment Type	Thermal Hyperalgesia –Eddy's hot plate method			
		Response Time (s)			
	Group Type	Reaction Latency (1st week)	Reaction Latency (2th weeks)	Reaction Latency (3th weeks)	Reaction Latency (4th weeks)
1	Normal Control	4.15 sec	4.23 sec	4.43 sec	4.11 sec
2	Diabetic Control	6.91 sec	7.24 sec	8.94 sec	9.95 sec
3	Standard 1 (Metformin)	6.12 sec	5.60 sec	5.01 sec	5.14 sec
4	Standard 2 (Pregabalin)	5.03 sec	5.11 sec	4.91 sec	4.88 sec
5	Treated (D+E)	6.01 sec	5.01 sec	4.21 sec	4.53 sec

The fourth week's response from Treatment Group IV revealed a mean reaction latency of 4.88 s and 4.53 s in Groups IV and V. When compared to Group II's (the diabetic control group) results from week 4, the results are noteworthy.

Effect of isoeugenol, eugenol, and their combination on heat hyperalgesia assessed by Eddy's hot-plate test. A $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. Significance is represented as * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, and *** $p < 0.001$; a—normal control versus diabetic control corresponding to the same day, b—diabetic control versus treatment groups corresponding to the same day.

8.3.2. Writhing Responses:

Table: 8.6 Effect diosgenin & eugenol on the writhing responses to assess the neuropathic pain in Wistar albino rats.

S. No.	Treatment Type	Number of Writhing Responses time in sec.			
	Group Type	(1 nd week)	(2 th week)	(3 th week)	(4 th week)
1	Normal Control	15.41	12.21	10.13	8.4
2	Diabetic Control	25.11	26.86	27.39	29.13
3	Standard 1 (Metformin)	21.14	24.13	23.44	18.54
4	Standard 2 (Pregabalin)	21.19	22.64	22.41	16.52
5	Treated (D+E)	20.17	21.28	20.17	14.81

In ten minutes, Group V had an average of 14.81 writhing responses, whereas Group IV demonstrated an average of 16.52. The findings were highly significant when compared to the responses from the fourth-week experimentation group (Group II), which was the diabetes control group. Table 18 mentions the outcomes.

Effect of isoeugenol, eugenol, and their combination on Writhing Responses test. A $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. Significance is represented as * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, and *** $p < 0.001$; a—normal control versus diabetic control corresponding to the same day, b—diabetic control versus treatment groups corresponding to the same day.

8.3.3. Cold Hyperalgesia (Acetone drop test)

Table: 8.7 Effect of diosgenin & eugenol on Cold hyperalgesia: Acetone drop test in Female wistar rats.

S. No.	Treatment Type	Cold Hyperalgesia (Acetone drop test)			
	Group Type	Allodynia Score in sec (1 st week)	Allodynia Score in sec (2 th week)	Allodynia Score in sec (3 th week)	Allodynia Score in sec (4 th week)
1	Normal Control	4.91	4.13	4.19	4.62
2	Diabetic Control	7.77	8.11	8.75	9.12
3	Standard 1 (Metformin)	5.28	4.98	4.37	6.98
4	Standard 2 (Pregabalin)	5.97	5.11	5.01	4.91
5	Treated (D+E)	4.93	4.84	4.76	4.53

The findings documentation is shown in Table 19. Group V's response to cold hyperalgesia was whereas Group IV's average readings were 4.91 when compared to the data from week 4. There was statistical significance in these differences. Group II, the group with diabetes, had extended reactions, whereas the group with diabetes-induced delayed responses in hyperalgesia suggested probable nerve damage.

Effect of isoeugenol, eugenol, and their combination on Acetone drop test. A $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. Significance is represented as * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, and *** $p < 0.001$; a—normal control versus diabetic control corresponding to the same day, b—diabetic control versus treatment groups corresponding to the same day.

8.3.4. Mechanical Hyperalgesia (Pin prick test)

Table: 8.8 Effect of diosgenin & eugenol on Mechanical hyperalgesia: Pin prick test in Female wistar rats.

S. No.	Treatment Type	Mechanical Hyperalgesia (Pin prick test)			
	Group Type	Response latency in sec (1 nd week)	Response latency in sec (2 th week)	Response latency in sec (3 th week)	Response late Response latency in sec (4 th week)
1	Normal Control	2.13	2.21	1.99	2.31
2	Diabetic Control	6.16	6.96	7.71	8.78
3	Standard 1 (Metformin)	6.86	7.98	8.92	4.99
4	Standard 2 (Pregabalin)	6.03	7.79	8.41	4.16
5	Treated (D+E)	6.44	7.94	4.05	3.11

The results are compared in Table 8. Group IV and Group V's responses have improved to 4.16 and 3.11, respectively, as compared to the data from week 4. When compared to the responses from the diabetic control group (Group II), which was the fourth-week experimentation group, the results were extremely significant.

Effect of isoeugenol, eugenol, and their combination on Pin prick test. A $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. Significance is represented as * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, and *** $p < 0.001$; a—normal control versus diabetic control corresponding to the same day, b—diabetic control versus treatment groups corresponding to the same day.

8.4. HbA1c:

Table 8.9 Effect of Diosgenin & Eugenol on HbA1c level of Female wistar rats.

	HbA1c nc						Stz+ dc						Stz+Met						Stz+Pre						Diosgenin+Eugenol					
DAY 0	4.1	3.4	3.6	3.7	3.6	3.8																								
DAY 7	4.7	4.1	4	4.4	4.2	4.7	9.1	10	9.7	9.4	8.3	8.9	7.2	6.8	7.8	7.6	8.1	7.9	8.9	9.1	8.8	9.4	9.6	9.7	8.6	8.4	10	8.8	8.7	8.7
DAY 14	5.1	4.3	4.2	4.5	4.7	4.9	9.9	10.7	10.2	9.9	9.7	9.8	6.6	5.8	6.4	6.1	7.2	6.3	7.8	8.7	8.1	8.4	8.3	9	7.5	7.1	8.9	7.6	7.4	7.5
DAY 21	5.9	4.7	4.6	5.1	5.3	5.8	10.7	11.4	11.2	10.8	10.1	10.8	5	5.1	5.3	5.7	6.3	5.2	6.5	7.6	7.4	7.2	7.1	8.4	6.4	6.6	7.4	6.4	6.4	6.2
DAY 28	6.2	5.5	5.4	5.7	5.9	6	11.6	12.9	12	12.1	11.4	12.4	3.9	4.1	4.3	4.5	5.2	4	5.8	6.1	6.3	6.4	5.8	7.3	5.4	5.7	6.2	5.4	5.6	5.3

Estimation of serum biochemical levels in diabetic neuropathy rats and potential of Diosgenin & Eugenol on glycated hemoglobin % (HbA1c%). Data are expressed as the mean ± SEM (n = 6) and were analyzed using one-way ANOVA and Kruskal–Wallis test, followed by Dunn’s test. NC, Normal control; DC, Diabetic control; Std, Standard, Diosgenin (20mg/kg, p.o.) + Eugenol (10mg/kg, p.o.) (* p < 0.05)

8.5. serum Insulin:

Table 8.10 Effect of diosgenin & eugenol on serum Insulin.

DAYS	serum Insulin normal (ng/ml)						stz + dc (ng/ml)						stz+met (ng/ml)						stz+Pre (ng/ml)						Diosgenin+eugenol (ng/ml)					
DAY 0	3.1	3.4	3.6	3.7	3.4	3.1	3.4	3.6	3.7	3.4	3.1	3.4	3.6	3.7	3.4	3.1	3.4	3.6	3.7	3.4	3.1	3.4	3.6	3.7	3.4	3.1	3.4	3.6	3.7	3.4
DAY 7	4.7	4.1	4	4.4	4.2	4.7	4.1	4	4.4	4.2	4.7	4.1	4	4.4	4.2	4.7	4.1	4	4.4	4.2	4.7	4.1	4	4.4	4.2	4.7	4.1	4	4.4	4.2
DAY 14	5.1	4.3	4.2	4.5	4.7	5.1	4.3	4.2	4.5	4.7	5.1	4.3	4.2	4.5	4.7	5.1	4.3	4.2	4.5	4.7	5.1	4.3	4.2	4.5	4.7	5.1	4.3	4.2	4.5	4.7
DAY 21	5.7	4.7	4.6	5.1	5.3	5.7	4.7	4.6	5.1	5.3	5.7	4.7	4.6	5.1	5.3	5.7	4.7	4.6	5.1	5.3	5.7	4.7	4.6	5.1	5.3	5.7	4.7	4.6	5.1	5.3
DAY 28	6.2	5.5	5.4	5.6	5.9	6.2	5.5	5.4	5.6	5.9	6.2	5.5	5.4	5.6	5.9	6.2	5.5	5.4	5.6	5.9	6.2	5.5	5.4	5.6	5.9	6.2	5.5	5.4	5.6	5.9

Estimation of serum biochemical levels in diabetic neuropathy rats and potential of Diosgenin & Eugenol on (A) Serum Insulin. Data are expressed as the mean \pm SEM (n = 6) and were analyzed using one-way ANOVA and Kruskal–Wallis test, followed by Dunn’s test. NC, Normal control; DC, Diabetic control; Std, Standard, Diosgenin (20mg/kg, p.o.) + Eugenol (10mg/kg, p.o.) (* p < 0.05)

Biomarkers:

Table 8.11 Effect of Diosgenin & Eugenol on Malonaldehyd Level, Reduced Glutathione (GSH), Glutathione Peroxidase Act (MDA), SOD and Catalase Concentration of the Brain in diabetic neuropathy Disease.

GSH

Normal Control Group	Diabetic Control Group	STZ+ Metformin Group	STZ+ Pregabalin Group	STZ+DE Group
9.7	4.8	11.6	12.1	9.12
9.5	5.9	12.5	9.86	9.7
8.7	6	8.9	11.1	10.1
9.5	3.9	9.5	10.8	8.9
10.1	4.3	10.12	10.2	11.2
10.8	3.9	8.8	9.2	10

All values are in Mean ± SEM, n=6 animals in each group. * p<0.05 as compared with a disease Control group using one-way ANOVA followed by multiple comparisons Dunnett’s test, p<0.05, *p < 0.01, **p < 0.001. # p<0.05 as compared with a normal control group using one-way ANOVA followed by multiple comparisons Dunnett’s test. Compared with the diabetic control group, Diosgenin, eugenol, Metformin and pregabalin treated subjects had significantly lower GSH levels

($p < 0.05$).

MDA

Normal Control Group	Diabetic Control Group	STZ+ Metformin Group	STZ+ Pregabalin Group	STZ +DE Group
27.5	49.8	29.3	31.3	30.7
28.2	51.1	31.2	30.1	28.6
24.2	47.8	27.8	28.4	27.4
24.9	52.9	32.5	29.7	29.2
30.5	50.8	28.9	28.9	29.1
30	46.9	30.5	30	28.2

All values are in Mean \pm SEM, $n=6$ animals in each group. * $p < 0.05$ as compared with a disease Control group using one-way ANOVA followed by multiple comparisons Dunnett’s test, $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.001$. # $p < 0.05$ as compared with a normal control group using one-way ANOVA followed by multiple comparisons Dunnett’s test. Compared with the diabetic control group, Diosgenin, eugenol, Metformin and pregabalin treated subjects had significantly increase MDA levels ($p < 0.05$).

SOD

Normal Control Group	Diabetic Control Group	STZ + Standard Treatment Metformin	STZ+ Pregabalin Group	STZ + DE Group
45.8	25.6	48.9	49.1	46.2
42.5	23.6	45.6	47.6	43.6
43.5	25.9	43.5	48.2	44.5
44.5	24.5	44.5	45.2	42.8
41.5	27.2	47.5	44.8	42
48.5	24.3	49.6	43.1	42.3

All values are in Mean ± SEM, n=6 animals in each group. * p<0.05 as compared with a disease Control group using one-way ANOVA followed by multiple comparisons Dunnett’s test, p<0.05, *p < 0.01, **p < 0.001. # p<0.05 as compared with a normal control group using one-way ANOVA followed by multiple comparisons Dunnett’s test. Compared with the diabetic control group, Diosgenin, eugenol, Metformin and pregabalin treated subjects had significantly lower SOD levels (p < 0.05).

CAT

Normal Control Group	Diabetic Control Group	STZ + Metformin	STZ+ Pregabalin Group	STZ+ DE Group
8.6	2.9	8.9	10.1	10.1
9.2	3.3	6.2	9.6	7.3
9.7	2.9	7.2	9.1	8.9
8.4	3.5	10.2	8.4	8.2
10.2	4.1	8.6	8.1	9.6
9.5	3.3	9	7.4	.8.1

All values are in Mean \pm SEM, n=6 animals in each group. * $p < 0.05$ as compared with a disease Control group using one-way ANOVA followed by multiple comparisons Dunnett's test, $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.001$. # $p < 0.05$ as compared with a normal control group using one-way ANOVA followed by multiple comparisons Dunnett's test. Compared with the diabetic control group, Diosgenin, eugenol, Metformin and pregabalin treated subjects had significantly lower CAT levels ($p < 0.05$).

8.6. Lipid profile

Albumin

Normal Control Group	Diabetic Control Group	DC+ Metformin Group	DC+ Pregabline Group	DC+ DE Group
3.59	4.44	3.86	2.99	3.58
3.7	4.6	3.59	3.07	3.68
3.59	5.07	3.7	3.6	3.53
3.57	5.19	3.73	3.55	3.61
3.73	5.04	3.97	4.52	3.43
3.65	5.12	3.6	4.04	3.48

Estimation of lipid profile of diabetic neuropathy rats and potential of diosgenin & eugenol on Albumin Data are expressed as the mean \pm standard error of the mean ($n = 6$) and were analyzed using one-way ANOVA and Kruskal–Wallis test, followed by Dunn’s test. NC, Normal control; DC, Diabetic control; Std. metformin; Std. Pregabalin & Diosgenin (20mg/kg, p.o.) + Eugenol (10mg/kg, p.o.) (* $p < 0.05$).

Triglycerides

Normal Control Group	Diabetic Control Group	DC+Metformin Group	DC+Pregabline Group	DC+ DE Group
206.32	419.42	248.41	169.38	127
200.29	450.33	217.95	174.09	208.02
193.52	406.76	195.58	90.5	143.04
202.45	349.52	191.75	107.43	174.24
204.34	304.34	198.55	176.6	181.89
219.422	410.12	230.16	140.39	220.22

Estimation of lipid profile of diabetic neuropathy rats and potential of diosgenin & eugenol on Triglyceride Data are expressed as the mean \pm standard error of the mean (n = 6) and were analyzed using one-way ANOVA and Kruskal–Wallis test, followed by Dunn’s test. NC, Normal control; DC, Diabetic control; Std. metformin; Std. Pregabalin & Diosgenin (20mg/kg, p.o.) + Eugenol (10mg/kg, p.o.) (* p < 0.05).

Uric Acid

Normal Control Group	Diabetic Control Group	DC+ Metformin Group	DC+Pregabline Group	DC+ DE Group
5.58	7.77	5.61	6.09	5.1
6.2	8.13	6.18	6.12	6.7
5.82	8.07	5.55	6.35	5.65
6.04	8.15	6	5.57	6.48
6.17	10.64	6.42	6.19	5.78
5.99	9.01	5.89	6.20	6.45

Estimation of lipid profile of diabetic neuropathy rats and potential of diosgenin & eugenol on Uric acid Data are expressed as the mean \pm standard error of the mean (n = 6) and were analyzed using one-way ANOVA and Kruskal–Wallis test, followed by Dunn’s test. NC, Normal control; DC, Diabetic control; Std. metformin; Std. Pregabalin & Diosgenin (20mg/kg, p.o.) + Eugenol (10mg/kg, p.o.) (* p < 0.05).

Total Protein

Normal Control Group	Diabetic Control Group	DC+ Metformin Group	DC+Pregabline Group	DC+DE Group
6.86	15.59	6.74	6.86	7.2
6.74	15.88	4.87	7.06	7.4
5.68	18.58	6.12	7.66	6.82
5.48	18.51	6.86	7.75	6.81
6.01	13.16	6.29	6.64	6.59
6.12	12.45	7.41	7.73	6.59

Estimation of lipid profile of diabetic neuropathy rats and potential of diosgenin & eugenol on Total Protein in Data are expressed as the mean \pm standard error of the mean ($n = 6$) and were analyzed using one-way ANOVA and Kruskal–Wallis test, followed by Dunn’s test. NC, Normal control; DC, Diabetic control; Std. metformin; Std. Pregabalin & Diosgenin (20mg/kg, p.o.) + Eugenol (10mg/kg, p.o.) (* $p < 0.05$).

Cholesterol

Normal Control Group	Diabetic Control Group	DC+Metformin Group	DC+ Pregabline Group	DC+ DE Group
200.07	425.6	208.6	145.7	197
245	629.1	213.9	163	196.9
255.09	666.4	277.5	174.1	259.4
207.7	244	263.8	178.7	259.4
210.04	227.3	200.6	217.4	244.7
256.9	455.3	278.6	217.9	246.1

Estimation of lipid profile of diabetic neuropathy rats and potential of diosgenin & eugenol on Cholesterol in Data are expressed as the mean \pm standard error of the mean (n = 6) and were analyzed using one-way ANOVA and Kruskal–Wallis test, followed by Dunn’s test. NC, Normal control; DC, Diabetic control; Std. metformin; Std. Pregabalin & Diosgenin (20mg/kg, p.o.) + Eugenol (10mg/kg, p.o.) (* p < 0.05).

Creatinine

Normal Control Group	Diabetic Control Group	DC+Metformin Group	DC+ Pregabline Group	DC+DE Group
0.8	2.46	1.5	2.35	3.33
0.45	3.6	1.4	2.17	2.73
0.75	3.3	0.98	3.82	2.75
1.3	4.89	1.22	2.44	3.10
1.2	3.7	1.35	2.35	2.55
1.1	4.96	2	3.74	2.39

Estimation of lipid profile of diabetic neuropathy rats and potential of diosgenin & eugenol on Creatinine Data are expressed as the mean \pm standard error of the mean (n = 6) and were analyzed using one-way ANOVA and Kruskal–Wallis test, followed by Dunn’s test. NC, Normal control; DC, Diabetic control; Std. metformin; Std. Pregabalin & Diosgenin (20mg/kg, p.o.) + Eugenol (10mg/kg, p.o.) (* p < 0.05).

CKMB

Normal Control Group	Diabetic Control Group	DC+Metformin Group	DC+Pregabline Group	DC+DE Group
5.5	30.2	10.2	24.05	13.05
7.5	25.6	12.6	21.25	15.5
6.05	32.5	13.5	18.13	16.6
9.56	33.22	10.2	22.27	10.5
10.2	28.6	14.2	22.3	11.3
12.6	28.52	12.6	17.5	11.33

Estimation of lipid profile of diabetic neuropathy rats and potential of diosgenin & eugenol on CKMB Data are expressed as the mean \pm standard error of the mean ($n = 6$) and were analyzed using one-way ANOVA and Kruskal–Wallis test, followed by Dunn’s test. NC, Normal control; DC, Diabetic control; Std. metformin; Std. Pregabalin & Diosgenin (20mg/kg, p.o.) + Eugenol (10mg/kg, p.o.) (* $p < 0.05$).

CRP

Normal Control Group	Diabetic Control Group	DC+Metformin Group	DC+Pregabline Group	DC+DE Group
1.42	1.52	0.5	1.2	2.03
0.98	2.62	0.96	2.26	1.43
0.56	4.78	1.3	2.5	1.51
1.32	3	2.5	1.33	1.42
1.2	2.63	1.56	1.85	1.39
0.79	3.98	2.03	2.05	1.35

Estimation of lipid profile of diabetic neuropathy rats and potential of diosgenin & eugenol on CRP Data are expressed as the mean \pm standard error of the mean ($n = 6$) and were analyzed using one-way ANOVA and Kruskal–Wallis test, followed by Dunn’s test. NC, Normal control; DC, Diabetic control; Std. metformin; Std. Pregabalin & Diosgenin (20mg/kg, p.o.) + Eugenol (10mg/kg, p.o.) (* $p < 0.05$).

8.7. Histopathology Result Of BRAIN

Figure 8.1: A. Section view of hippocampus region of brain from **control (C) group** showing normal architectural components of hippocampus includes; cornu ammonis (CA1, CA2, CA3) and Dentate Gyrus (DG) (H & E, x40). **B.** Section of hippocampus region of brain from **Diabetic group** showing severe decrease cellular population in dentate gyrus region (H & E, x40).

C. Section of hippocampus region of brain from **Diabetic + Metformin** showing decrease cellular population (arrow) in dentate gyrus region and vacuolation in neuropil as compared to control group (H & E, x100) **D.** Section of cerebral cortex region of brain from **Diabetic + Pregabalin group** showing degenerating hyper eosinophilic neurons (Dn) with presence of satellite cells and astrocytic satellite cells (As) (H & E, x400) **E.** Microscopic section of brain of **Diosgenin & Eugenol group** showing vacuolated (black arrow) and degenerative changes in the brain cortex. **Note:** Neuropil is also vacuolated (H & E Stain X 400).

8.8 PANCREAS:

Figure 8.2: A. Microscopic section of Pancreas of **Normal Control group** showing normal architecture. Note: Normal Population of **Exocrine Cell- α cell** and **Endocrine part - β cell**. (H & E Stain X 400) B. Microscopic section of Pancreas of **Diabetic group** showing severe

decrease the Population and degeneration and necrosis of - β cell compared to control group. (H & E Stain X 40) C. Microscopic section of Pancreas of Diabetic group + Metformin showing mild increase the Population and degeneration and necrosis of of - β cell compared to control group. (H & E Stain X 400) D. Microscopic section of Pancreas of Diabetic + Pregabalin showing mild decrease the Population and necrosis of - β cell compared to Diabetic group. (H & E Stain X 100) E. Microscopic section of Pancreas of Diosgenin & Eugenol group showing mild increase the Population and necrosis of - β cell compared to Diabetic group.

8.9 SCIATIC NERVES:

Figure 8.3: Longitudinal vasa nervorum analysis in sciatic nerves of wistar albino rats in all groups on 4th week. Representative the images from the sciatic nerve longitudinal section of the control group, diabetic group, standard pregabalin, standard Metformin and treated 1 groups from 1st week of treatment age. The samples were stained with eosin. Group II shows swelling in the neurons. Effects of diosgenin & eugenol obtained on the eosin histopathological sections

of sciatic nerves in diabetic rats. Following figures indicating: **A**: Normal nerve tissue which is not showing any sign of inflammation or degenerative changes in the control group (non-diabetic). **B**: Lipid degenerated axons showing focal peripheral axonal loss in case of diabetic group (untreated); **C**: mild focal axonal loss in the peripheral region in standard group; **D**: mild focal axonal loss in the peripheral region in standard group **E**: minimum axonal degeneration changes in treated group with diosgenin & eugenol.

8.10 LIVER:

Figure 8.4: **A.** Section of liver from **Normal control group** showing almost normal architecture of hepatic lobules (H & E x 400). **B.** Section of liver from **Diabetic group** showing vacuolar degeneration and necrosis in hepatocytes (black arrow). The hepatic cords are also severely distorted. (H & E x 40). **C.** Section of liver from **Diabetic + Std Metformin group** showing moderately vacuolar degeneration and necrosis in hepatocytes (black arrow) as compared to

diabetic group. The hepatic cords are also less distorted as compared to diabetic group as well as congestion in central vein is also noted (red arrow). (H & E x 100). **D.** Section of liver from **Diabetic + Std + Pregabalin group** showing mild vacuolar degeneration and necrosis in hepatocytes (black arrow) as compared to diabetic group. The hepatic cords are also less distorted as compared to diabetic group. (H & E x 100). **E** Section of liver from **Diosgenin + Eugenol group** showing mild congestion of central vein (black arrow) and mild vacuolar degeneration of hepatocytes (Yellow arrow) (H & E, x100) **Note:** Mild Sinusoidal congestion is also noted

8.11. KIDNEY:

Figure 8.5: **A.** Section of kidney from **normal control group** showing normal architecture of kidney. (H & E x 100). G-Glomeruli, T-Tubules. **B.** Section of kidney from **Diabetic group** showing increase in glomerulus diameter and Bowman's space (Yellow arrow) as well as increased number of proximal tubules with necrosis nuclei as compared to control group. (H & E

x 100). **C.** Section of kidney from **Diabetic + Diosgenin + Eugenol** showing mild increase in Bowman's space (Yellow arrow) as well as mild degenerative changes in the proximal tubular epithelium as compared to control group. (H & E x 100) **D.** Section of kidney from **Diabetic + Pregabalin** showing increase in glomerulus diameter and Bowman's space (Yellow arrow) as well as increased number of proximal tubules with necrosis nuclei as compared to control group. (H & E x 100) **E.** Section of kidney from **Diabetic + Diosgenin + Eugenol** showing mild increase in Bowman's space (Yellow arrow) as well as mild degenerative changes in the proximal tubular epithelium as compared to control group. (H & E x 100).

Conclusions:

Because of the decreased threshold to painful stimuli and the heightened nociceptive response, diabetic neuropathy caused by STZ presents with allodynia and hyperalgesia. In addition to these behavioral tests, the animals also displayed clinicopathological characteristics such as biochemical, oxidative, and metabolic abnormalities. The pinprick test, grip strength, acetone drop test, Writhing response, and hot plate method are among the techniques used to document behavioral study of animals with diabetic neuropathy produced by STZ. Animals with persistent long-term diabetes lose paw withdrawal latency because of neuronal sensitization brought on by damage to motor and sensory fibers. Animals treated with diosgenin and eugenol showed a dose-dependent amelioration of their lower pain threshold compared to normal animals. These outcomes are consistent with earlier research.

The most common symptom of diabetes mellitus that contributes to complications like DN is hyperglycemia. Research has verified that hyperglycemia causes hemoglobin to become glycosylated (HbA1c), and that this elevated HbA1c level is associated with advanced glycosylated end-products (AGEs) that are linked to delayed wound healing or neuronal damage. In DN rats, treatment with diosgenin and eugenol considerably lowered the HbA1c and blood glucose levels in a dose-dependent manner. In rats given a high-fat, high-cholesterol diet, diosgenin and eugenol lower hypercholesterolemia.

Without changing the amount of HDL cholesterol, it also decreases plasma LDL and triglycerides and inhibits HMG-CoA reductase. This means that by overexpressing AMPK, underexpressing important gluconeogenic enzymes, and decreasing HMG-CoA reductase activity, diosgenin and eugenol lower the metabolic syndrome. ROS accumulation and lipid peroxidation are reduced by diosgenin and eugenol. Diosgenin and eugenol reduce SOD, GSH, and catalase activity to increase antioxidant defense system activity-induced oxidative stress in HFD/STZ-induced diabetic rats with hyperglycemia. MDA is primarily responsible for breaking down lipid membranes by upsetting the double bond in the membrane's unsaturated fatty acids, which ultimately damages the tissues. MDA levels in DN rats were higher than in treated groups. Lipid

peroxidation is enhanced, indicating increased oxidative stress that was mitigated by medication. Superoxide and hydroxyl radicals are the main causes of damage to vascular endothelial cells. SOD protects against these radicals by converting them into H₂O₂. The antioxidant capability of diosgenin and eugenol was demonstrated by the remarkable restoration of these antioxidant enzymes' altered levels in DN rats. Recent studies have shown a substantial correlation between inflammation and neuropathic pain after nerve damage.

Numerous conditions that damage peripheral nerves, including immunological and metabolic disorders, diabetes, infections, and drug-induced neuropathy, can cause neuropathic pain, a complex sickness. Peripheral nerves are the source of almost all neuropathic pain types. The spinal cord and sensory neurons in peripheral nerves that react to pain are remarkably flexible. Proinflammatory cytokines participate in the immune response's activation and steer it in the right direction. Nevertheless, these inflammatory mediators may damage myelin, alter the permeability of the blood-nerve barrier (BNB), and directly increase neuronal excitability. These effects could result in edema and further immune cell infiltration.

Proinflammatory cytokines are often associated with increased sensory afferent excitability, demyelination and degeneration of peripheral neurons, and development of neuropathic pain. Anti-inflammatory drugs with inflammatory reactions can be used to manage inflammation, a complicated biological process involving vascular tissue responding to tissue damage, damaged cells, infections, or irritants. Inflammation can result in autoimmune illnesses. Numerous preclinical and clinical investigations have demonstrated the harmful function of inflammation, including the generation of chemokines and cytokines in DN.

Our findings showed that against STZ-induced DPN in rats, diosgenin and eugenol have antihyperglycemic, antioxidative, and anti-inflammatory effects. Furthermore, morphological analyses showed that the sciatic nerve damage brought on by STZ was significantly lessened after diosgenin and eugenol were administered. Furthermore, the damage caused by STZ-induced DN in rats was significantly reduced after diosgenin and eugenol were administered in a dose-dependent manner, according to behavioral

and histological tests of the brain and pancreas. This study showed that in diabetic neuropathic rats, diosgenin and eugenol positively alleviated oxidative and inflammatory mediators as well as decreased nerve activity. These results suggest that these substances may be used to treat diabetic peripheral nerve injury.

More investigation is required to comprehend the processes underlying their protective benefits and ascertain whether they could be exploited as therapeutic agents for diabetic neuropathy. Research on novel routes of DN pathogenicity, as well as the safety and effectiveness of eugenol and diosgenin in humans, is anticipated to broaden the uses of these substances in the prevention and treatment of numerous illnesses. Expanding the therapeutic potential of diosgenin and eugenol in people and creating novel pathogenic signaling pathways for DN will help these chemicals become more effective and safe.

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Institutional Review Board Statement: This study was conducted according to the guidelines of the Committee for Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals (CPCSEA) and approved by the Institutional Animal Ethical Committee (IAEC), Department of Pharmacology, Krishna School of Pharmacy (Formerly, Babaria Institute of Pharmacy), Drs. Kiran and Pallavi Patel Global University, Krishna Edu Campus, Varnama, Vadodara, Gujarat, India.

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